

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**SEROPREVALENCE OF HEPATITIS C VIRUS IN LOCAL
PEOPLE OF LAHORE DIVISION****Muhammad Khalid, Muhammad Usman Haider, Arshad Karim**

Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College, Sialkot

Dera Ghazi Khan Medical College, Dera Ghazi Khan

Sharif Medical and Dental College, Lahore

Article Received: April 2020**Accepted:** May 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: The hepatitis C virus is an important public health problem and is a leading etiological factor in chronic liver disease worldwide. Chronic hepatitis C virus infection is persistent and asymptomatic disease in humans can cause cirrhosis, fibrosis and hepatocellular carcinoma. This study was conducted to determine the prevalence of anti-HCV antibodies by ELISA in the general population of Lahore.

Place and Duration: In the Medical departments of Mayo Hospital Lahore for one year duration from January 2019 to January 2020.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was designed containing 2,800 serum samples from the general population in Lahore. Samples were analyzed for anti-HCV antibodies by enzyme-linked immunoassay (ELISA) and alanine aminotransferase (ALT) levels were also assessed for positive samples. The results were statistically analyzed using SPSS 16.0. The chi-square test and fisher's test was used to find a relationship between various variables such as age group, gender and area.

Results: Of the 2,800 subjects, 1,872 men (66.8%) and 928 women (32.2%) were analyzed to detect anti-HCV antibodies. Among 2,800 people, 196 (7.0%) were positive for anti-HCV antibodies. A relationship between anti-HCV antibodies for sex and region was observed. There was no significant difference between ELISA and gender. Only anti-HCV antibodies in the 41-50 age group differed significantly in p-values (<0.05) in the ELISA. The highest average ALT (alanine aminotransferase) observed was 77.3 IU / L among 41-50 age group.

Conclusions: In this study, we attempted to determine the incidence of anti-HCV antibodies in the general population in Lahore and concluded that the incidence of anti-HCV infection was 7% in the study population. We recommend routine testing for anti-HCV antibodies by ELISA, which can help reduce the transmission of HCV infection.

Keyword: Seroprevalence, anti-HCV antibodies, ELISA, ALT,

Corresponding author:**Muhammad Khalid,**

Khawaja Muhammad Safdar Medical College, Sialkot

QR code

Please cite this article in press Muhammad Khalid et al., **Seroprevalence Of Hepatitis C Virus In Local People Of Lahore Division., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(06).**

INTRODUCTION:

Hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection is an important public health problem worldwide. Acute hepatitis C is often asymptomatic cause's chronic hepatitis and can be a major cause of morbidity and mortality. First, HCV discovered in 1989 in molecular biology techniques as the main cause of hepatitis. Hepatitis C virus is the causative agent of chronic liver disease that develops cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma is uncontrollable and deadly all over the world¹⁻³. The frequency of chronic HCV infection is affected by age, gender, race, and viral immune response⁴⁻⁶. It is estimated that about 170 million people are chronically infected with HCV, which is 3% of the world's population. The highest prevalence of HCV infection (10-20%) in the general population was recorded in Egypt⁷. It is estimated that chronic HCV infection is responsible for 250,000 to 300,000 deaths annually worldwide, and 3-4 million people are diagnosed each year as a new case. However, 50% to 85% of infected people go from acute to chronic, and 15% self-cleaning HCV. However, the incidence and incidence of acute HCV infection is difficult to determine because most patients with acute infection are asymptomatic. Once infected, a chronic infection can progress to liver scarring (fibrosis) and liver cirrhosis. Most patients have a relatively mild disease with a slow progression of HCV infection. Some studies have shown that hepatitis C infection causes a chronic infection that leads to serious complications such as cirrhosis, fibrosis and liver failure, the last stage of liver cancer. Chronic HCV infection accounts for 27% of liver cirrhosis and 25% of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), but liver cirrhosis is considered irreversible. The seroprevalence of anti-HCV antibodies is not well known due to insufficient research, and there have been several reports of the occurrence of HCV. HCV seroprevalence has been reported to be 4-10% in Pakistan. Some studies have shown that seroprevalence of HCV infection varies in different regions of Pakistan, for example, around 9% in Mardan, 13.33% in DI Khan, 17.77% in Faisalabad and 4-6% in Karachi. HCV is endemic in Pakistan and around the world. The incidence of anti-HCV antibodies is high in Pakistan due to the reuse of contaminated syringes, the use of shaving razors, hairdressers, contaminated blood products and dangerous blood transfusions, dental procedures, surgical instruments without hemodialysis and sterilization. The main source of hepatitis C infection is infected blood, blood products and body fluids⁹⁻¹⁰. An anti-HCV antibody testing system has been developed to diagnose HCV infection. In recent decades, significant progress has been made in identifying anti-HCV antibodies. The most commonly used tests for the diagnosis of HCV infection are anti-HCV antibodies by ICT, ELISA or

PCR and HCV RNA. An anti-HCV antibody using an immune-chromatographic test (ICT) and an enzyme immunoassay (ELISA) does not distinguish between acute and chronic cases of HCV or resolved infection. This test can be used to confirm or test for false-positive HCV results. This study was conducted to determine the prevalence of anti-HCV antibodies by ELISA in the general population of Lahore.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This survey was held in the Medical departments of Mayo Hospital Lahore for one year duration from January 2019 to January 2020. A total of 2,800 people were selected. Both sexes (men and women) aged 18-60 years from six different districts / regions and tested for anti-HCV using an ELISA kit (ACON Laboratories, Inc., USA). The kit was used to measure the level of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) by the enzymatic method (DiaSys diagnostic system). 2,800 people have been grouped by sex, age and region. The study population was divided into four different age groups: group 1 (18-30 years), group 2 (31-40 years), group 3 (41-50 years) and group 4 (51-60 years). Men constituted 1872 (66.8%) and women 928 (33.2%) respectively. However, patients under 18 years of age and over 60 years of age were not included in the study. ALT levels > 40 IU / L were considered abnormal and normal up to 40 IU / L. Mean ALT values were observed in individuals in the ELISA positive and age groups. An approved survey was developed to collect demographic data, including age, gender and area. Sterile disposable syringes were used to collect blood samples from 2,800 patients. Blood samples were rotated at 3000 rpm and serum / plasma separated. All samples were analyzed for anti-HCV antibodies by an enzyme immunosorption assay (ELISA) according to the production instructions. Samples of positive anti-HCV antibodies were analyzed by ELISA to determine the level of alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and ALT assessment was performed according to the production instructions.

Statistical analysis: The results were statistically analyzed using the SPSS 16.0 Chi-square version. The fisherman test was also used to find a relationship between various variables such as age group, gender and area. In this study, a P value below 0.05 ($P < 0.05$) was considered statistically significant, and a value above 0.05 ($P > 0.05$) was considered not significant.

RESULTS:

Anti-HCV antibodies were detected in both sexes. Of the general population, 196 people (7.0%) were positive for anti-HCV antibodies in the ELISA (Table 1). Seroprevalence did not differ significantly in gender and region ($P > 0.05$) using ELISA, but an

increase in the incidence of anti-HCV antibodies was found in men (7.5%) compared to women (5.9%). A very significant relationship between the age groups ($p < 0.05$) was found in the 41-30 age group (8.8%), in the 18-30 age group (4.2%), and in the 31-40 age group (5.5%). and 51-60 (7.3%), respectively. It was also noted that seroprevalence

with age group 4 (51-60 years) 8.8% was higher than age group 1 (18-30 years), 2 (31-40 years) and 4 (51-60) respectively (table 1). There was no statistically significant difference between areas ($P > 0.05$). All positive samples were analyzed for ALT levels. High ALT (> 40 IU / L) was observed (Table 2).

Table 1 Seroprevalence of anti-HCV antibodies by gender, age among the target area of general population of Balochistan

Characteristics	=n	Anti-HCV+ve cases by ELISA (%)
Gender		
Male	1872 (66.8%)	141 (7.5%)
Female	928 (33.2%)	55 (5.9%)
Age		
18-30 years	432 (15.43%)	18 (4.2%)
31-40 years	581 (20.75%)	32 (5.5%)
41-50 years	1059 (37.82%)	93 (8.8%)*
51-60 years	728 (26.00%)	53 (7.3%)
Area		
Shahdra	700 (25.00%)	49 (7.0%)
Mangamandi	450 (16.07%)	29 (6.4%)
Mughalpura	500 (17.86%)	38 (7.6%)
Inner Lahore	525 (18.75%)	41 (7.8%)
Thokar Niaz baig	350 (14.06%)	24 (6.9%)
Bahria	275 (11.94%)	15 (5.5%)
Total	2800	196 (7.0%)

P Value=0.006

Table 2 Age wise distribution of mean ALT level (IU/L) of the anti-HCV antibodies positive subjects by ELISA

Age Group	=n	Mean ALT IU/L (STD)
18-30 years	18	57.50±7.73
31-40 years	32	64.81±17.94
41-50 years	93	73.80±16.15
51-60 years	53	68.96±16.64
Total	196	69.5±16.7

DISCUSSION:

Hepatitis C infection is endemic in Pakistan, but ranges from 1.18 to 4.8%. This study was conducted on the general population of Lahore in Pakistan, and the ELISA test found a high incidence and disturbing HCV antibody infection (7%) in the general population and comparable to studies reported in other countries and regions. Previous studies on anti-HCV antibodies have been conducted among blood donors in various regions of Pakistan¹¹. A cross-sectional study was conducted among volunteer blood donors in Quetta

Belochistan, the percentage of seroprevalence anti-HCV antibodies was 1.85%, but the percentage of rejected blood donors based on an interview was 8.2%. The incidence of anti-HCV antibodies did not differ in gender and region, but was found to increase significantly in the 3-year age group and in people over the age of 50¹². Among people under the age of 50 years anti-HCV antibodies were seen 4.2% over 18 to 30 years, 5.5% up to a maximum of 8.8% over a period of 31-40 years. Topics from 41 to 50 years old. This is 7.3% among people aged 51-60 (Table 1). Our results are consistent with the results

reported by some employees in the middle-aged group between 40 and 50 years of age. The high incidence of anti-HCV antibodies that increase with age group and other risk factors may be due to the fact that diseases are not aware of infected syringes, hair salons, and the use of contaminated instruments, dangerous blood transfusions or economic problems. Some other studies have reported the highest percentage of HCV infections in people over the age of 40¹³. The results of this study regarding the prevalence of anti-HCV antibodies were 8.8% at 41-50 years old, which is less than the prevalence rate reported for HCV infection aged 40-59 years, 65% and 50% in the 30-49 age group in the US States. In this study, a higher incidence of anti-HCV antibodies was observed in the male population than in the female population. Our findings can be compared with the results reported by other employees. Similarly, other studies have shown a higher percentage of men than women. There are large differences in the prevalence of anti-HCV antibodies worldwide. About 10 million people in Pakistan live with chronic HCV infection. The global incidence of HCV is 3%, and there may be over 170 million patients with chronic HCV infection worldwide, with between 3 and 4 million people being diagnosed each year¹⁴. In this study, the incidence of anti-HCV antibodies was observed as 7%, and this can be compared with studies reported in other countries, e.g. 17.77% in Faisalabad, 10% in Islamabad and 20% such as Egypt. In this study, the overall incidence of anti-HCV antibodies was reported at 7.0% by ELISA in patients in different regions [Table 1]. Some studies have shown that HCV seropositivity is strongly associated with male gender and old age. This study found a strong association with the age group¹⁵. The characteristic feature of the ALT pattern changes in the course of acute hepatitis. Normalization of ALT values may occur and indicates that HCV is eliminated or that the patient is completely cured. Elevation of ALT indicates chronic HCV infection and is a serious medical threat and requires immediate treatment. Predicted positive cases have a great impact on the occurrence of the disease. In this study, among the total number of patients, 196 people with a positive ELISA test had an upper limit or elevated ALT. Average serum ALT levels in individuals with a positive HCV result were higher in age group of 3. Many studies have reported high HCV infection in developing countries where resources for diagnosis, prevention and treatment of diseases are very limited or inaccessible. The HCV screening center is only offered in some higher hospitals and is not available at basic or medium level due to insufficient resources for healthcare and lack of public health awareness and poor approach. About Pakistan's disease¹⁵. It is well known that in immunocompromised patients, serological tests may be negative, even in the form of a positive viral

load due to a poor immune response. These patients can spread the disease despite low viral load. ELISA kits are suitable for underdeveloped countries such as Pakistan due to the lack of appropriate facilities such as infrastructure and limited resources. However, no diagnostic test for HCV provides 100% accuracy. As a result, additional tests can be used to confirm the anti-HCV antibody test result, such as PCR.

CONCLUSION:

The study found that HCV infection persists in the Lahore population and is also comparable to Pakistan and other developing regions. Prior to invasive procedures, which are one of the main risk factors responsible for the spread of hepatitis C, routine serological detection is missing in our regional hospitals. In addition, we recommend that district hospitals be equipped with screening to reach most patients. Target population throughout the province.

REFERENCES:

1. Lodhi, Ammara, Ashif Sajjad, Khalid Mehmood, Ayesha Lodhi, Sabeena Rizwan, Ayesha Ubaid, Kulsoom Baloch, Sheikh Ahmed, and Zahid Mehmood. "Profile and predictors of hepatitis and HIV infection in patients on hemodialysis of Quetta, Pakistan." *Drug discoveries & therapeutics* 13, no. 5 (2019): 274-279.
2. Pathan, Navish Lodhi, Sarfraz Ali Tunio, Shaista Bano, and Abdul Nabi Jatt. "15. Frequency distribution of hepatitis C virus genotypes circulating in Hyderabad, Sindh." *Pure and Applied Biology (PAB)* 8, no. 1 (2019): 133-138.
3. Mehmood, Shahid, Hassan Raza, Farhan Abid, Nouman Saeed, Hafiz Muzzammel Rehan, Safdar Javed, and Muhammad Saleem Khan. "National prevalence rate of hepatitis B and C in Pakistan and its risk factors." *Journal of Public Health* (2019): 1-14.
4. Haqqi, Aleena, Rimsha Munir, Muhammad Khalid, Muhammad Khurram, Muhammad Zaid, Muhammad Ali, Zaheer Hussain Shah, Haroon Ahmed, and Muhammad Sohail Afzal. "Prevalence of Hepatitis C Virus Genotypes in Pakistan: Current Scenario and Review of Literature." *Viral immunology* 32, no. 9 (2019): 402-413.
5. Akhtar, Sohail, Jamal Abdul Nasir, Muhammad Usman, Aqsa Sarwar, Rizwana Majeed, and Baki Billah. "The prevalence of hepatitis C virus in hemodialysis patients in Pakistan: A systematic review and meta-analysis." *Plos one* 15, no. 5 (2020): e0232931.
6. Jan, Naveed, Zia Ur Rahman Awan, and Mehboob Ur Rahman Awan. "Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) infection in general population of

- District Bannu Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. Pure and Applied Biology. Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp1679-1689." (2020).
7. Wali, Ahmad, Dawood Khan, Nauman Safdar, Zeenat Shawani, Razia Fatima, Aashifa Yaqoob, Aurangzeb Qadir et al. "Prevalence of tuberculosis, HIV/AIDS, and hepatitis; in a prison of Balochistan: a cross-sectional survey." *BMC Public Health* 19, no. 1 (2019): 1-8.
 8. Akhtar, Sohail, Jamal Abdul Nasir, and Andrew Hinde. "The prevalence of hepatitis C virus infection in β -thalassemia patients in Pakistan: a systematic review and meta-analysis." *BMC Public Health* 20 (2020): 1-9.
 9. Farooq, Muhammad, Noorbakhat Ahmad, and Salman Saleem. "Prevalence of the Hcv Infection and Age or Gender Related Association in Hcv-Positive Patients from General Population of Lahore Pakistan." *Pakistan Armed Forces Medical Journal* 69, no. 4 (2019): 905-10.
 10. Naqvi, Iftikhar Haider, Abu Talib, Gohar Baloch, Khalid Mahmood, and Zahid Qadari. "HEPATITIS B AND C: FREQUENCY, MODES OF TRANSMISSION AND RISK FACTORS ALONG WITH SOME UNORTHODOX ROUTES OF SPREAD." *Pakistan Journal of Public Health* 9, no. 3 (2019): 161-165.
 11. Rehm, Muhammad Hassam, Raees Abbas Lail, Rana Aamir Diwan, Sajid Hameed, and Muhammad Punoon. "Sero-Prevalence of Hepatitis B and C Among Blood Donors Visiting DHQ Teaching Hospital, Sahiwal." In *Med. Forum*, vol. 31, no. 4. 2020.
 12. Khan, Muhammad Imran, Fakhra Batool, Fadia Kalsoom, and Ahsan Kazmi. "Qurat-ul-ain Zahra, Muhammad Bilal, Rizwan Ali, Ajikia Zaman Juthi, Hafiz MN Iqbal, Undiagnosed Hepatitis B and C Virus Infection at a Teaching Hospital in Rawalpindi." *J. Pure Appl. Microbiol* 14, no. 2 (2020).
 13. Siddique, Muhammad, Muhammad Shafique, Abdul Mateen, Naveed Shahzad, Bilal Aslam, Nasir Ahmad, and Muhammad Usman Qamar. "Prevalence and Genotypic Analysis of Hepatitis C Virus Isolated from Liver Center, Faisalabad, Pakistan." *Pakistan Journal of Zoology* 52, no. 1 (2020): 313-319.
 14. Naeem, Muhammad, Arif Malik, Qurban Ali, Muhammad Khalid, Samrah Masud, and Arif Mahmood Bhutta. "Hepatitis B and C prevalence and its associated risk factors among school going children in urban and rural areas of District Muzaffar Garh, Pakistan." *Genetics and Molecular Research* 19, no. 1 (2020).
 15. Kumar, Tanweer, Sahib Zada, Muhammad Irfan, Huma Batool, and Wasim Sajjad. "Serological Prevalence of Hepatitis B Virus in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan." *Pakistan Journal of Zoology* 52, no. 2 (2020): 525.